

PSYCHOLOGICAL CHARACTERISTICS OF THE FORMATION OF LEARNING MOTIVATION IN ADOLESCENT PERIOD

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Abstract. The article describes the analysis of theoretical and practical views on the specific aspects of educational activities during adolescence. Also, researches of foreign scientists on educational motivation in adolescence are described. Empirical issues of the formation of learning motivation during adolescence have been explained.

Key words: educational activity, education, personal motive, motivation, motivation of educational activity, need, interest, goal, stimulus (incentives), tendency, ustanovka, communicative motives, self-avoidance motives, prestige motives, professional motives, self -motives of self-creative expression, motivations related to knowledge and study, social motives.

Аннотация. Мақолада ўсмирлик даврида ўқув фаолиятининг ўзига хос жиҳатларига доир назарий ва амалий қарашларнинг таҳлиллари баён қилинган. Шунингдек, ўсмирлик даврида ўқув мотивациясига доир хориж олимларининг изланишлари баён қилинган. Айниқса, ўсмирлик даврида ўқув мотивациясини шаклланишининг эмпирик масалалари изоҳлаб берилган.

Калит сўзлар: ўқув фаолияти, таълим, шахс мотив, мотивация, ўқув фаолияти мотивацияси, эҳтиёж, қизиқиш, мақсад, стимул (рағбат)лар, мойиллик, установка, коммуникатив мотивлар, ўзини олиб қочиш мотивлари, обрў-этибор мотивлари, касбий мотивлар, ўз-ўзини ижодий намоён қилиш мотивлари, билишга ва ўқишга оид мотивлар, ижтимоий мотивлар.

Абстрактный. В статье представлен анализ теоретических и практических взглядов на конкретные аспекты учебной деятельности в подростковом возрасте. Также описаны исследования зарубежных ученых по вопросам учебной мотивации в подростковом возрасте. Объяснены эмпирические вопросы формирования мотивации обучения в подростковом возрасте.

Ключевые слова: учебная деятельность, воспитание, личностный мотив, мотивация, мотивация учебной деятельности, потребность, интерес, цель, стимул (стимулы), тенденция, установка, коммуникативные мотивы, мотивы самоизбегания, мотивы престижа, профессиональные мотивы, самомотивы, самотворческого самовыражения, мотивы, связанные с познанием и учебной, социальные мотивы.

It is known that, considering the motivation of educational activities, it is necessary to emphasize that the concept of motive is inextricably linked with the concepts of purpose and need. In the human personality, they have an interaction and are called the motivational sphere. In the literature, this term includes all types of triggers: needs, interests, goals, incentives, motives, inclinations, attitudes.

Learning motivation is defined as a specific type of motivation embedded in a specific activity - in this case, learning activity. Learning motivation, as any type, is determined by a number of factors and specific characteristics of the activity in which it is included. First, it is determined by the educational system, the educational institution itself; secondly, with the organization of the educational process; thirdly, with the subjective characteristics of the learner; fourth, with the subjective characteristics of the pedagogue and, first of all, with the system of his relationship to the learner; fifth, with the uniqueness of the educational subject [1].

Learning motivation, like any of its types, is systematic and characterized by direction, stability and dynamism.

Thus, in the works of L.I. Bojovich and his colleagues, based on the research materials of students' educational activities, learning motivation is dominated by either internal motives related to the content of this activity and its implementation, or broad social motives related to the child's need to occupy a certain place in the system of social relations. evokes a sequence of motifs that can do.

The teaching material and teaching methods should be varied enough (but not too much). Diversity is provided not only by students encountering different objects in the learning process, but also by discovering new aspects in a single object. One of the ways to arouse the curiosity of students is to "digress", that is, to show students an unexpected, important, new thing in their usual way of life. The novelty of the material is the most important condition for interest in it. However, the knowledge of the news must rely on the knowledge that the student already has. The use of previously acquired knowledge is one of the main conditions for the emergence of interest. An important factor that creates interest in educational material is that it has an emotional tone [2].

These cases formulated by S. M. Bondarenko can serve as a specific program for organizing an educational process specially focused on the formation of interest. Various types of interest, for example, consequential, cognitive, procedural, educational, understanding, etc., can be compared with motivational orientation (E.I. Savonko, N.M. Simonova).

According to B.I. Dodonov, the characteristics of the relationship between motivational orientations allow us to distinguish two important characteristics:

firstly, the orientation to the process and results, on the one hand, and, on the other hand, the stability of relations between the orientation to "teacher evaluation" and "avoidance of failure" (according to the criterion of stability), that is, their relative independence from educational conditions; secondly, the variety of connections depending on the educational conditions (according to the criteria of priority and "weight"), hours, features of the curriculum, in particular, target institutions, etc. [3]. A positive relationship between motivational orientation (according to the reliable level of significance) and mastery in adolescence was found. Mastery has a stronger relationship with process and outcome orientation, and a weaker relationship with "teacher evaluation" orientation. There is a weak correlation between mastery and a "disappointment avoidance" orientation.

It should be noted that it is important to study the manifestation of academic motivation in adolescence. For example, the level of formation of educational motivation in a teenager is to be determined. Therefore, we conducted the methodology "Diagnostics of learning motivation of students" (modified by N.S. Badmaeva) developed by A.A.Rean and V.A.Yakunin in the test groups. With the help of this methodology, it is possible to determine the level of formation of the following structural aspects of educational motivation in the group of test subjects: communicative motives, self-avoidance motives, prestige motives, professional motives, motives for self-creative expression, motives related to knowledge and study, and social motives. this methodology was carried out in the group of teenagers, the obtained data were analyzed quantitatively and qualitatively, and the obtained results were presented in tables and diagrams in order to clearly express them.

Table 1

Indicators of the formation of educational motivation during adolescence

Testers	Communicative motives	Self-escape motives	Reputation motives	Professional motives	Motives of creative self-expression	Motives for learning and learning	Social motives
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7th grade	13,8%	-	5,7%	39,1%	25,3%	6,9%	9,2%
9th grade	13,3%	-	6,7%	40%	20%	6,7%	13,3%

According to the results of the methodology, 13.8% of 7th grade students and 13.3% of 9th grade students recorded high scores on the scale of communicative motives. Communication characteristics are the main motivation for the study of this category of teenagers. For them, they prefer to study in order to make new acquaintances and communicate with interesting people, and to become a person worthy of attention in the educational community. Also, according to them, the knowledge gained during studies increases self-confidence.

5.7% of the 7th grade students and 6.7% of the 9th grade students were noted for reputation motives. For such teenagers, gaining status and prestige is the main motivation for studying. The factors that motivate them to study include being among the best teenagers, wanting their group to be the best group in higher education, being a good role model in the eyes of teachers, and gaining the attention of parents and others.

The scale of professional motivations of this methodology was recorded in the 7th and 9th grade students compared to others. According to it, it was found that 7th grade students have 39.1%, and 9th grade students have 40%. Becoming a mature expert in their profession is the main motivation for such students. The factors that cause them to study are the following: they like their chosen profession, the desire to ensure the success of their future work, to become a mature specialist, to be able to answer questions related to the field of future work, to fully use all their abilities and skills related to their chosen profession, the desire to become a highly qualified specialist, etc.

In the test group, 25.3% of 7th grade students and 20% of 9th grade students scored high on the scale of self-creative self-expression motives. The main motive in the study of such teenagers indicates that they have a high desire and desire to work creatively on themselves. Therefore, they receive education in order to acquire new knowledge and engage in creative activities, to respond to problems in the development of society and people's life activities. In addition, students of this category always try to reveal their hidden abilities during their studies, work tirelessly on themselves, and make full use of their opportunities.

6.9% of 7th-grade students and 6.7% of 9th-grade students showed high results on the scale of "motivation to learn and study". The desire to learn at a deep level serves

as the main motivation for studying for adolescents who have high scores on this scale. Among the factors that motivate such teenagers to study, it is possible to include such things as good studies, passing exams with "4" and "5" marks, simply enjoying studying, always being ready for the next lesson, answering questions about studying clearly, and realizing that various knowledge is necessary in the field of their future.

According to the seventh scale of the methodology - the scale of social motives, 9.2% of students of the 7th grade and 13.3% of the students of the 9th grade were recorded. The main motive influencing the study of teenagers who have recorded high results on this scale is the desire to find their place in society. Such teenagers believe that the knowledge they have acquired will help them achieve their desired goals, they emphasize that the level of future material security depends on their success in their studies, and that the knowledge they have acquired in the current educational process has a great impact on their future professional activities. They are also educated in order to be of great benefit to society and to repay their debt to their parents and teachers.

According to the results of the research, it was found that there were no indicators of self-avoidance motives in the test group. It can be seen that, in any case, it is explained by the active pursuit of educational activities during adolescence. From the point of view of ontogenetic development, we must not forget that reading is the leading activity during adolescence.

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